

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

LEGAL, INFRASTRUCTURE, AND TECHNOLOGICAL BARRIERS TO THE TRANSITION TO A CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN UNDERDEVELOPED COUNTRIES AND POTENTIAL STRATEGIES FOR OVERCOMING THEM

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Abstract

The transition to a circular economy (CE) in underdeveloped countries faces several barriers, including legal, infrastructure, and technological challenges. This article discusses the main issues slowing this process, such as the lack of legal initiatives, weak recycling infrastructure, and limited access to modern technologies. Strategies for overcoming these barriers are proposed, including the development of national strategies, the creation of tax incentives for businesses and the development of recycling capacities. Special attention is given to the role of international organizations in supporting the transition to circular models.

Keywords: circular economy (CE), underdeveloped countries, barriers, legislation, technology, sustainable development (SD).

Introduction

The circular economy (CE) is a concept that aims at maximum utilization of resources by reusing, recycling, and waste reduction. In the context of global climate change, resource depletion, and an ever-increasing environmental crisis, this concept is gaining importance. However, there are many obstacles to the implementation of the principles of CE, especially in underdeveloped countries. These barriers arise as a result of legal restrictions, underdeveloped infrastructure, and limited access to modern technologies. In this regard, a review of the existing challenges and development of effective strategies for overcoming these issues have to be done.

The purpose of this article is to examine the legal, infrastructural, and technological barriers hindering the transition to a CE in underdeveloped countries. It also explores possible strategies and approaches to address these challenges. Special attention is given to analyzing international experience and the prospects of adapting successful practices in the context of these countries' limited resources and economic constraints. Such an approach aims to identify viable solutions that contribute to building a sustainable economy on a global scale.

Main part. Overview of the current situation and key barriers

In underdeveloped countries, adoption of a CE is a big step toward sustainable development (SD), but faces serious obstacles. **Legal issues** are among the main barriers to the large-scale CE practice. Most underdeveloped countries lack legislation on waste recycling and do not offer enough incentives for the use of recycled materials. The absence of regulations and standards on waste and resource management means that businesses lack clear guidelines on how to operate within a circular model. Further, the inefficient implementation of the law enforcement and corruption nullify the existing law many times, while non-availability of tax breaks or any incentives for a CE enterprise makes them suffer a lot.

Infrastructure barriers are another major obstacle to the implementation of CE. In most cases, waste collection and recycling systems in these countries are not developed, resulting in the accumulation of waste that is often dumped in landfills where it is not recycled (fig.1).

Fig. 1. Waste Recycling Efficiency Index (EPI) in 2024: a comparison between underdeveloped and developed countries [1]

Countries like Switzerland, Japan, France, and the USA develop high values of the EPI, explained by their well-developed infrastructure for recycling waste, strict environmental laws, and effective legislation. In these countries, a high level of waste recycling is included in the CE, supported by investments in technology and the public.

In contrast, the EPI values for countries like Mozambique, the Central African Republic, Mali and

Burkina Faso are far lower. These countries face a number of infrastructural barriers to recycling: an absence of recycling facilities, a weak transportation network for collecting and sorting garbage, and lack of access to modern technologies. Besides, low investment and a lack of government support are further deterrents to the adoption of sustainable practices. As a result of these barriers, secondary waste recycling rates in underdeveloped countries, according to the latest data from 2022, remain low (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. EPI recycling score in 2022

Although in some undeveloped countries the formal recycling rate is quite high, figures are primarily based on organic waste being the biggest proportion of total volume. Being the easiest one to handle, some process in organic waste yields fertilizers used by farmers, which is why inflated recycling statistics may exist. The infrastructure for the recycling of complex materials such as plastics or electronics is so bad that the rates of recycling remain very low. In such countries, one of the most crucial reasons regarding inefficiency in waste management processes relates to infrastructural barriers.

Technological barriers represent another major challenge. Despite the existence of new technologies that can significantly improve material recycling, many underdeveloped countries do not have access to its [2]. According to the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) in its 2023 report, some countries developing recycling initiatives lack access to modern waste recycling technologies due to high initial costs and difficulties in adapting technologies to local conditions. For example, **Tajikistan** has made progress in SD, including GDP growth and the use of green energy (fig.3).

Fig. 3. The total volume of renewable energy in Tajikistan, MW [3]

Nevertheless, the country faces several challenges on its path toward transitioning to a CE, including the low adoption of modern waste recycling technologies. For instance, in Tajikistan, the use of solutions such as automated sorting lines and biomechanical processing facilities remains extremely limited. For comparison, Tajikistan's EPI in 2024 was estimated at 3,1, while Switzerland, the leader in the ranking, scored 100. Ad-

ditionally, limited access to funding and high costs associated with importing equipment hinder the development of waste recycling. These challenges are further exacerbated by a lack of qualified specialists and weak integration of scientific research into waste management practices. To overcome these barriers, targeted investments, international collaboration, and the adaptation of technologies to regional conditions are essential.

Strategies for overcoming legal barriers

Legal barriers are one of the major impediments to switching toward a CE in underdeveloped countries. Special features of countries, such as underdevelopment of their legal system, one-sidedness, and fragmented environmental legislation and a weak institutional framework, seriously complicate the application of the principles of sustainability. But even in most cases, when existing, the legislation is too declarative and thus too inefficient to organize regulative functions concerning waste recycling or other eco-friendly technologies diffusion and many other processes necessary

for the development of CE principles. Furthermore, the low level of enforcement makes even existing regulations ineffectively applied. Insufficient financial and technical opportunities impede substantially the adaptation of successful solutions developed in countries with more developed economies. Under these conditions, it is necessary to work out strategies considering the socio-economic and institutional realities of the underdeveloped countries to overcome the legal barriers in such a transition to a CE (table 1).

Table 1

Strategies for overcoming legal barriers to transitioning to a CE in underdeveloped countries [4, 5]

Strategy	Description	Examples of implementation
Development and modernization of legislation	Adoption of laws regulating waste recycling, reducing carbon emissions, and providing tax incentives for companies applying CE principles.	Rwanda banned the use of plastic bags and single-use plastics, encouraging a shift to sustainable materials.
Enhancing transparency and accountability	Establishing monitoring mechanisms, national registries of waste management enterprises, and improving reporting.	Ghana implemented an electronic waste tracking system to enhance transparency and promote recycling.
Strengthening institutional infrastructure	Creating government agencies to coordinate CE initiatives and attract international technical assistance.	Bangladesh organized state structures to support waste recycling in the textile industry.
Simplifying regulatory procedures	Reducing administrative barriers for companies adopting sustainable practices.	Kenya simplified licensing procedures for recycling businesses, fostering growth in the sector.
Raising legal awareness and public participation	Educating the population on CE principles and creating mechanisms for community involvement in environmental projects.	South Africa launched educational campaigns on waste sorting, raising public awareness and participation.
Integrating CE principles into national strategies	Embedding CE goals into national development plans and supporting innovation in sustainable technologies.	Uganda integrated CE principles into its National Green Growth Strategy, supporting SD.

The rationale is to overcome the legal barriers also in underdeveloped countries because it is supposed to be systematic and long-term. At the first level, a regulatory effective framework should provide, after some time, rules regarding waste recycling, adoption of innovative technologies, reduction of carbon footprint, etc. The legislative change is not just sufficient merely by its introduction. This can be provided for through the reinforcement of institutional support by creating special government agencies with responsibility for coordinating implementation according to CE strategies, while viewing sustainability as an approach. Besides, there is also the social aspect-eliciting the population and business for transitioning towards sustainability. This is only possible with mechanisms for education and inclusion, which can help foster sustainable public behavior.

Infrastructure and technology strategies

Transition to CE in underdeveloped countries is to be provided by complex efforts aimed at developing both legislative initiatives, on one hand, and infrastructure with new technologies' introduction, on the other. Regarding this, attention should be paid to both improvement in already existing waste-processing systems and also to the introduction of such innovative approaches that could enhance the efficiency of processing with a lesser environmental impact.

Most underdeveloped countries lack infrastructure for collecting, sorting, and recycling waste, which can be explained by low living standards, widespread poverty, and, in some cases, the fight against hunger. Nevertheless, it is necessary to build waste recycling plants, organize waste sorting centers, and enhance transport logistics for efficient material flow; even in conditions of low living standards and limited resources, such efforts can help improve sanitary conditions, create jobs, and reduce dependence on imported materials. This is especially important for underdeveloped countries where socio-economic challenges are especially sharp.

An illustrative example is the **Zabbaleen** community in Cairo, Egypt. Despite facing economic hardships, they have developed one of the world's most efficient recycling systems, manually sorting and repurposing waste into products like jewelry and textiles. Remarkably, the Zabbaleen recycle about 80% of the waste they collect, significantly surpassing recycling rates in many developed countries [6].

Another case is **Bangladesh's Waste Concern**, a social business enterprise founded in 1996. Operating in a resource-constrained environment, Waste Concern has implemented decentralized community-based composting systems that transform organic waste into compost.

India is a successful example of such approaches, actively implementing innovative technologies under

the **Swachh Bharat Mission Urban 2.0** (SBM-U 2.0) program. One of the country's key strategies has been the development of waste-to-energy plants, such as the one in the Tehkand district, which processes municipal waste and generates electricity for urban needs. This initiative has not only improved sanitary conditions but also created employment opportunities and reduced reliance on chemical fertilizers.

These examples demonstrate that, even in underdeveloped countries with limited resources, establishing waste recycling facilities and improving waste management systems can lead to significant environmental and socio-economic benefits. In the future, it will be possible to implement, even in underdeveloped countries, innovative technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and use it as a strategy to overcome infrastructure and technological barriers for the transition to a CE. IoT allows efficient resource management through the digitalization of waste collection, sorting, and recycling processes, which becomes especially important in conditions of limited infrastructure. For instance, the usage of smart sensors in waste collection

systems will optimize transportation routes by reducing the costs and carbon footprint [7]. In addition, IoT technologies can be used in the management and monitoring of energy consumption at recycling plants for further efficiency. The only solution is to improve the population's digital literacy and attract investment and international assistance in creating conditions and infrastructure that allow such solutions to be effectively implemented.

The role of the international community

The international community has a critical role to play in promoting CE, particularly in underdeveloped countries where domestic resources and capacity to implement such practices are limited. Investments in these countries, including through international mechanisms such as the Green Climate Fund (GCF) and the Global Environment Facility (GEF), help overcome barriers associated with high upfront costs of technology solutions and infrastructure. Moreover, private and public investment, particularly through public-private partnerships, are becoming key to implementing long-term strategies for the transition to circular models (table 2).

Table 2

Circular investment economy funds by instrument category, sector and value [8]

Investor	Sector	Instrument	Adjusted value (€ million)
Intesa Sanpaolo	Circular business models	Debt; guarantees	6,000.00
BlackRock	Mixed	Public equities	1,700.00
Archipelago Eco Investors	Plastics/packaging	Private equity	1,500.00
Lloyds Bank	Mixed	Investor commitments	1,484.74
Credit Suisse Rockefeller	Circular oceans	Public equities	1,276.91
ABN AMRO	Mixed	Debt; guarantees	1,000.00
Ambient	Resource efficiency	Private equity	668,84

International agreements and organization shave a significant impact on the development of the CE in resource-poor countries. One prominent example is the initiative of the **United Nations Environment Programme** (UNEP), which launched a project in 2023 to support low- and middle-income countries in the transition to circular models.

The project includes financial assistance, exchange of best practices and technical support for the establishment of effective waste management systems. The program also promotes awareness of CE and helps develop national waste management and resource recycling strategies. Thus, the international community, through financial and technical assistance, as well as through international agreements and knowledge sharing, plays a key role in supporting the transition to CE in underdeveloped countries.

Conclusion

Promoting CE in underdeveloped countries requires a comprehensive approach combining legal, infrastructural, and technological strategies with active cooperation with the international community. It should be taken into consideration, however, that significant challenges include the weak development of recycling infrastructures, and restricted access to modern technologies is slowing down the pace at which the CE principles could be implemented in underdeveloped countries.

Overcoming these barriers will require a comprehensive approach: from the creation of national strategies and infrastructure development to the introduction of innovative technologies. Legislative initiatives, such as tax incentives and the establishment of recycling standards, might stimulate businesses to switch to circular models. Building capacities in recycling and the development of new technologies will contribute to increased efficiency in recycling and diminishing environmental impact.

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